

1 Bimatrix games that include interaction times alter the
2 evolutionary outcome: The Owner–Intruder game

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9 **Abstract**

Classic bimatrix games, that are based on pair-wise interactions between two opponents in two different roles, do not consider the effect that interaction duration has on payoffs. However, interactions between different strategies often take different amounts of time. In this article, we further develop a new approach to an old idea that opportunity costs lost while engaged in an interaction affect individual fitness. We consider two scenarios: (i) individuals pair instantaneously so that there are no searchers, and (ii) searching for a partner takes positive time and populations consist of a mixture of singles and pairs. We describe pair dynamics and calculate fitnesses of each strategy for a two-strategy bimatrix game that includes interaction times. Assuming that distribution of pairs (and singles) evolves on a faster time scale than evolutionary dynamics described by the replicator equation, we analyze the Nash equilibria (NE) of the time-constrained game. This general approach is then applied to the Owner–Intruder bimatrix game where the two strategies are Hawk and Dove in both roles. While the classic Owner–Intruder game has at most one interior NE and it is unstable with respect to replicator dynamics, differences in pair duration change this prediction in that up to four interior NE may exist with their stability depending on whether pairing is instantaneous or not. The classic game has either one (all Hawk) or two ((Hawk,Dove) and (Dove,Hawk)) stable boundary NE. When interaction times are included, other combinations of stable boundary NE are possible. For example, (Dove,Dove), (Dove,Hawk), or (Hawk,Dove) can be the unique (stable) NE if interaction time between two Doves is short compared to some other interactions involving Doves.

10 *Keywords:* Evolutionary game theory, Hawk–Dove game, Pair formation,
11 Time-scale separation, Time-constrained games

12 **1. Introduction**

13 Classic evolutionary game theoretical models in normal form consider two
14 players with a finite number of strategies and a payoff matrix. Players in a
15 large (infinite) population meet at random, interact pair-wise, and obtain
16 their corresponding (individual) fitnesses. There are three important and
17 somewhat hidden assumptions: (i) interaction times between two strategies
18 are not considered, i.e., they are all assumed to be the same, (ii) the dis-
19 tribution of strategy pairs corresponds to random pair formation among all
20 individuals and (iii) individual fitness accrues only through pair interactions.
21 These assumptions fit genetic population models with two (or more) alleles at
22 a single locus. In the genetic model, the alleles pair randomly during meiosis
23 and the resulting distribution of genotypes is given by the Hardy–Weinberg
24 equation. When alone, alleles cannot gain any fitness. For many phenotypic
25 models (e.g., the Hawk–Dove, or Prisoner’s dilemma), these assumptions are
26 likely not satisfied. For example, when two aggressive individuals are in a
27 fight, their interaction can be much longer when compared to the situation
28 where one individual (a Dove) exits from an interaction with a Hawk (in
29 which case the Hawk will win the contest). Because contests between differ-
30 ent strategies can take different times, the resulting equilibrium distribution
31 of pairs does not correspond to the Hardy–Weinberg equation.

32 Křivan and Cressman (2017) showed that, when individuals pair instan-
33 taneously but the interaction times are strategy dependent, the Hawk–Dove
34 model may have a mixed ESS (i.e., an evolutionarily stable state that consists
35 of a mixture of Hawks and Doves) when the cost of a fight is lower than the
36 value of the contested resource. For this to happen, the interaction time be-
37 tween two Hawks must be long enough relative to interaction times between
38 other strategies. Such an outcome is not possible in the classic Hawk–Dove
39 game that does not consider interaction times. Similarly, for the repeated
40 Prisoner’s dilemma, provided cooperators stay together for enough rounds of
41 the game while pairs with at least one defector disband quickly, cooperation
42 does evolve (Křivan and Cressman, 2017). This situation arises naturally if
43 players can choose whether to continue the game to the next round with the
44 same opponent, since it is always better to play against a cooperator than

45 a defector in the Prisoner’s dilemma game (see also the opting-out game
46 (Zhang et al., 2016)).

47 Moreover, individuals can gain/lose fitness when alone (e.g., individuals
48 with different strategies may have different mortalities). While the above
49 games do not consider singles, Křivan et al. (2018) assumed that pairing be-
50 tween individuals is not immediate and being single has fitness consequences.
51 They showed that distributional dynamics alone can lead to density depen-
52 dence in models (e.g., the Hawk–Dove model) that are only frequency depen-
53 dent when pairing is instantaneous and all interaction times are the same.

54 All the models considered above are based on symmetric games (in par-
55 ticular, matrix games), where the two contestants are assumed to be drawn
56 from the same population and can differ only in their choice of strategy.
57 It is well known that various asymmetries (Broom and Rychtář, 2013) in
58 contestants lead to qualitatively different outcomes when interaction times
59 are not considered. A class of asymmetric games, bimatrix games, where
60 the two contestants are drawn from two different types of individuals (e.g.,
61 two populations or two roles) was studied thoroughly in the literature (e.g.,
62 Hofbauer and Sigmund, 1998; Cressman, 2003; Broom and Rychtář, 2013).
63 A well-known result of classic evolutionary game theory for these games is
64 that no interior evolutionarily stable strategy exists (Selten, 1980) (i.e., no
65 ESS where each population is a mixture of pure strategies). Furthermore,
66 bimatrix games may have an interior Nash equilibrium (NE) but it cannot be
67 asymptotically stable under the (bimatrix) replicator equation, the standard
68 game dynamics of evolutionary game theory (Hofbauer and Sigmund, 1998).
69 In particular, ESSs and asymptotically stable equilibria correspond to strict
70 NEs of the bimatrix game (i.e., pure strategy pairs where both players do
71 strictly worse by unilaterally changing their strategy).

72 Given the conceptual differences between the evolutionary outcomes of
73 classic matrix and bimatrix games, it is important to understand the con-
74 sequences of strategy-dependent interaction times by extending the analysis
75 beyond the matrix games considered by Křivan and Cressman (2017). To this
76 end, in this article, we study the effect of interaction time on the evolution-
77 ary outcome of bimatrix games when both populations have two strategies.
78 We consider two pair formation processes based on the assumption that the
79 number of individuals of each population are the same. In Section 2, as
80 existing pairs disband, these individuals instantaneously form new pairs ran-
81 domly among themselves. From the analytic expression of the equilibrium
82 distribution of pairs at a given number of each strategy in both populations,

83 we analyze the resulting game (i.e., investigate its NEs and their stability)
 84 when individual fitness is defined as expected payoff per unit time. When
 85 interaction times are all the same, we recover the classic results. Otherwise,
 86 more complicated evolutionary outcomes emerge such as multiple interior
 87 NEs (some of which are stable and some unstable) as well as strict NE that
 88 differ from the classic game. These possibilities are illustrated there by a
 89 thorough analysis of the Owner–Intruder game (Broom and Rychtář, 2013),
 90 the bimatrix version of the Hawk–Dove game where individuals assume one
 91 of the two roles, owner or intruder.

92 In Section 3, when pairs disband, the resulting singles form new pairs at
 93 random through the mass action principle with a finite encounter rate. Since
 94 the analytic expression of the equilibrium distribution of pairs at a given
 95 number of each strategy in both populations is no longer tractable unless all
 96 interaction times are the same, we analyze the Owner–Intruder game, with
 97 unequal interaction times, numerically.

98 2. Instantaneous pair formation

99 We consider a bimatrix game with two strategies denoted by e_i ($i = 1, 2$)
 100 for the row player in population 1 and f_j ($j = 1, 2$) for the column player in
 101 population 2. The payoff bimatrix is

$$\begin{array}{cc} & \begin{array}{cc} f_1 & f_2 \end{array} \\ \begin{array}{c} e_1 \\ e_2 \end{array} & \left[\begin{array}{cc} \pi_{11}^e, \pi_{11}^f & \pi_{12}^e, \pi_{12}^f \\ \pi_{21}^e, \pi_{21}^f & \pi_{22}^e, \pi_{22}^f \end{array} \right] \end{array} \quad (1)$$

102 where π_{ij}^e (respectively, π_{ij}^f) is the payoff to e_i (respectively f_j) when interact-
 103 ing with f_j (respectively e_i). In contrast to classic evolutionary game theory,
 104 we explicitly incorporate the duration of interactions into the game through
 105 the time interaction matrix

$$\begin{array}{cc} & \begin{array}{cc} f_1 & f_2 \end{array} \\ \begin{array}{c} e_1 \\ e_2 \end{array} & \left(\begin{array}{cc} \tau_{11} & \tau_{12} \\ \tau_{21} & \tau_{22} \end{array} \right) \end{array} \quad (2)$$

106 where τ_{ij} is the expected time two players using strategy e_i and f_j stay
 107 together.

108 In this section, we assume that, when pairs split, all these newly single
 109 individuals immediately form new pairs at random. We are interested in the

110 equilibrium distribution of strategy pairs (e_i, f_j) for given numbers of the
 111 different strategies. Let n_{ij} be the number of strategy pair (e_i, f_j) . As shown
 112 in Appendix A, pair dynamics are

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{dn_{11}}{dt} &= -\frac{n_{11}}{\tau_{11}} + \frac{\left(\frac{n_{11}}{\tau_{11}} + \frac{n_{12}}{\tau_{12}}\right) \left(\frac{n_{11}}{\tau_{11}} + \frac{n_{21}}{\tau_{21}}\right)}{\frac{n_{11}}{\tau_{11}} + \frac{n_{12}}{\tau_{12}} + \frac{n_{21}}{\tau_{21}} + \frac{n_{22}}{\tau_{22}}} \\
 \frac{dn_{12}}{dt} &= -\frac{n_{12}}{\tau_{12}} + \frac{\left(\frac{n_{11}}{\tau_{11}} + \frac{n_{12}}{\tau_{12}}\right) \left(\frac{n_{12}}{\tau_{12}} + \frac{n_{22}}{\tau_{22}}\right)}{\frac{n_{11}}{\tau_{11}} + \frac{n_{12}}{\tau_{12}} + \frac{n_{21}}{\tau_{21}} + \frac{n_{22}}{\tau_{22}}} \\
 \frac{dn_{21}}{dt} &= -\frac{n_{21}}{\tau_{21}} + \frac{\left(\frac{n_{21}}{\tau_{21}} + \frac{n_{22}}{\tau_{22}}\right) \left(\frac{n_{11}}{\tau_{11}} + \frac{n_{21}}{\tau_{21}}\right)}{\frac{n_{11}}{\tau_{11}} + \frac{n_{12}}{\tau_{12}} + \frac{n_{21}}{\tau_{21}} + \frac{n_{22}}{\tau_{22}}} \\
 \frac{dn_{22}}{dt} &= -\frac{n_{22}}{\tau_{22}} + \frac{\left(\frac{n_{21}}{\tau_{21}} + \frac{n_{22}}{\tau_{22}}\right) \left(\frac{n_{12}}{\tau_{12}} + \frac{n_{22}}{\tau_{22}}\right)}{\frac{n_{11}}{\tau_{11}} + \frac{n_{12}}{\tau_{12}} + \frac{n_{21}}{\tau_{21}} + \frac{n_{22}}{\tau_{22}}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

113 and the equilibrium distribution satisfies

$$\frac{n_{ij}}{\tau_{ij}} = \frac{\left(\frac{n_{i1}}{\tau_{i1}} + \frac{n_{i2}}{\tau_{i2}}\right) \left(\frac{n_{1j}}{\tau_{1j}} + \frac{n_{2j}}{\tau_{2j}}\right)}{\left(\frac{n_{11}}{\tau_{11}} + \frac{n_{12}}{\tau_{12}} + \frac{n_{21}}{\tau_{21}} + \frac{n_{22}}{\tau_{22}}\right)} \quad \text{for } i, j = 1, 2. \tag{4}$$

114 Intuitively, at equilibrium, the number of disbanding (e_i, f_j) pairs per unit
 115 time (i.e., the left-hand side $\frac{n_{ij}}{\tau_{ij}}$ of (4)) must equal the number of newly
 116 formed (e_i, f_j) pairs from the newly single e_i strategists $\left(\frac{n_{i1}}{\tau_{i1}} + \frac{n_{i2}}{\tau_{i2}}\right)$ and f_j
 117 strategists $\left(\frac{n_{1j}}{\tau_{1j}} + \frac{n_{2j}}{\tau_{2j}}\right)$.

118 We observe that at the equilibrium distribution, $\frac{n_{ij}}{\tau_{ij}}$ satisfy the generalized
 119 Hardy–Weinberg equation, i. e.,

$$\frac{n_{11}}{\tau_{11}} \frac{n_{22}}{\tau_{22}} = \frac{n_{12}}{\tau_{12}} \frac{n_{21}}{\tau_{21}}. \tag{5}$$

120 Given the number of e_1 and f_1 strategists ($N_{e_1} = n_{11} + n_{12}$ and $N_{f_1} = n_{11} + n_{21}$,
 121 respectively) as well as the total number of individuals $N = n_{11} + n_{12} + n_{21} +$
 122 n_{22} in either population, Appendix A shows that the unique nonnegative

123 solution to (4) and (5) is (assuming $\tau_{12}\tau_{21} \neq \tau_{11}\tau_{22}$)

$$\begin{aligned}
n_{11} &= \frac{\sqrt{A} + (N_{e_1} + N_{f_1})(\tau_{12}\tau_{21} - \tau_{11}\tau_{22}) - N\tau_{12}\tau_{21}}{2(\tau_{12}\tau_{21} - \tau_{11}\tau_{22})}, \\
n_{12} &= \frac{-\sqrt{A} + (N_{e_1} - N_{f_1})(\tau_{12}\tau_{21} - \tau_{11}\tau_{22}) + N\tau_{12}\tau_{21}}{2(\tau_{12}\tau_{21} - \tau_{11}\tau_{22})}, \\
n_{21} &= \frac{-\sqrt{A} - (N_{e_1} - N_{f_1})(\tau_{12}\tau_{21} - \tau_{11}\tau_{22}) + N\tau_{12}\tau_{21}}{2(\tau_{12}\tau_{21} - \tau_{11}\tau_{22})}, \\
n_{22} &= \frac{\sqrt{A} - (N_{e_1} + N_{f_1})(\tau_{12}\tau_{21} - \tau_{11}\tau_{22}) + N(\tau_{12}\tau_{21} - 2\tau_{11}\tau_{22})}{2(\tau_{12}\tau_{21} - \tau_{11}\tau_{22})},
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

124 where

$$A = (N\tau_{12}\tau_{21} - (N_{e_1} + N_{f_1})(\tau_{12}\tau_{21} - \tau_{11}\tau_{22}))^2 + 4N_{e_1}N_{f_1}\tau_{11}\tau_{22}(\tau_{12}\tau_{21} - \tau_{11}\tau_{22}). \tag{7}$$

125 When $\tau_{12}\tau_{21} = \tau_{11}\tau_{22}$ the above distributional equilibrium corresponds to
126 the standard Hardy–Weinberg distribution

$$(n_{11}, n_{12}, n_{21}, n_{22}) = \left(\frac{N_{e_1}N_{f_1}}{N}, \frac{N_{e_1}N_{f_2}}{N}, \frac{N_{e_2}N_{f_1}}{N}, \frac{N_{e_2}N_{f_2}}{N} \right) \tag{8}$$

127 where $N_{e_2} \equiv N - N_{e_1}$ and $N_{f_2} \equiv N - N_{f_1}$. This is an important special case
128 since it includes the classic situation, i.e., all interaction times are the same
129 ($\tau_{11} = \tau_{12} = \tau_{21} = \tau_{22}$).

130 2.1. Fitness and evolutionary outcomes

131 Following Křivan and Cressman (2017), we define fitness as the expected
132 payoff that an individual of a given phenotype obtains per unit of interaction
133 time. For example, let us consider an individual playing strategy e_1 in pop-
134 ulation 1. The probability that this individual is paired with an individual
135 playing strategy f_1 is $n_{11}/(n_{11} + n_{12})$ and with an individual playing strategy
136 f_2 is $n_{12}/(n_{11} + n_{12})$. When paired with an individual playing strategy f_1 ,
137 the focal individual receives payoff π_{11}^e/τ_{11} per unit of time. Similarly, when
138 paired with an individual playing strategy f_2 , the focal individual gets payoff
139 π_{12}^e/τ_{12} per unit of time. Thus, the focal individual has expected payoff (i.e.,
140 fitness) Π_{e_1} given by the first equation in (9). The fitness for individuals
141 playing e_2 and those in the second population are calculated analogously,

142 which leads to $(i, j = 1, 2)$

$$\begin{aligned}\Pi_{e_i} &= \frac{n_{i1}}{n_{i1} + n_{i2}} \frac{\pi_{i1}^e}{\tau_{i1}} + \frac{n_{i2}}{n_{i1} + n_{i2}} \frac{\pi_{i2}^e}{\tau_{i2}} \\ \Pi_{f_j} &= \frac{n_{1j}}{n_{1j} + n_{2j}} \frac{\pi_{1j}^f}{\tau_{1j}} + \frac{n_{2j}}{n_{1j} + n_{2j}} \frac{\pi_{2j}^f}{\tau_{2j}}.\end{aligned}\tag{9}$$

143 The corresponding time-constrained bimatrix game based on payoff bimatrix
144 (1) and time interaction matrix (2) is then the two-strategy game with payoffs
145 given by the fitness functions (9) evaluated at the distributional equilibrium
146 (6) for fixed size N of each population.¹

147 To analyze this time-constrained bimatrix game, we examine how its NE
148 structure depends on model parameters. We start by looking for NE in pure
149 strategies (i.e., both populations are monomorphic) before considering NE
150 where both populations are polymorphic (i.e., the interior NE later in this
151 section) and boundary NE (where exactly one population is polymorphic) in
152 Section 2.3. Let us consider the equilibrium where all individuals of popu-
153 lation 1 play strategy e_1 while all individuals of the second population play
154 strategy f_1 . Then $n_{11} = N$ and fitnesses of residents are $\Pi_{e_1} = \frac{\pi_{11}^e}{\tau_{11}}$ and
155 $\Pi_{f_1} = \frac{\pi_{11}^f}{\tau_{11}}$. Now consider a mutant of the first population playing strategy
156 e_2 in the resident system. This mutant can pair only with f_1 -strategists in
157 which case its fitness is $\Pi_{e_2} = \frac{\pi_{21}^e}{\tau_{21}}$. Similarly, $\Pi_{f_2} = \frac{\pi_{12}^f}{\tau_{12}}$. Thus, the strategy
158 (e_1, f_1) cannot be invaded if $\frac{\pi_{21}^e}{\tau_{21}} < \frac{\pi_{11}^e}{\tau_{11}}$ and $\frac{\pi_{12}^f}{\tau_{12}} < \frac{\pi_{11}^f}{\tau_{11}}$, in which case (e_1, f_1) is
159 a strict NE.² Similar considerations for other pure strategy pairs show that
160 a strategy (e_i, f_j) is a strict NE for the fitness functions given in (9) if it is a
161 strict NE of the classic game given by a time-adjusted payoff bimatrix

$$\begin{array}{cc} & \begin{array}{cc} f_1 & f_2 \end{array} \\ \begin{array}{c} e_1 \\ e_2 \end{array} & \left[\begin{array}{cc} \frac{\pi_{11}^e}{\tau_{11}}, \frac{\pi_{11}^f}{\tau_{11}} & \frac{\pi_{12}^e}{\tau_{12}}, \frac{\pi_{12}^f}{\tau_{12}} \\ \frac{\pi_{21}^e}{\tau_{21}}, \frac{\pi_{21}^f}{\tau_{21}} & \frac{\pi_{22}^e}{\tau_{22}}, \frac{\pi_{22}^f}{\tau_{22}} \end{array} \right].\end{array}\tag{10}$$

¹We will use the phrase “fitness functions” rather than “payoffs” for these time-constrained games from now on to avoid confusion with payoffs in (1).

²If (e_1, f_1) is a strict NE, it must also resist invasion by mutants in population 1 that use any other strategy (including a mixed strategy) besides e_1 . However, since the fitness of the focal mutant is linear in the components of its mixed strategy, it is enough to verify (e_1, f_1) cannot be invaded by the pure strategy e_2 (and by f_2 in population 2).

162 We remark that the inequality conditions for a strict NE are independent of
 163 population size. Furthermore, the fitness functions (9) when the populations
 164 are not monomorphic are convex combinations of the appropriate entries in
 165 the time-adjusted payoff bimatrix (e.g., $\Pi_{e_1} = \alpha \frac{\pi_{i1}^e}{\tau_{11}} + (1 - \alpha) \frac{\pi_{i2}^e}{\tau_{12}}$ for some
 166 $0 \leq \alpha \leq 1$). It is the same for the classic bimatrix game except that for
 167 us α is no longer a linear function of the strategy frequencies of the other
 168 population since the distributional equilibrium is not the standard Hardy–
 169 Weinberg distribution. In fact, α depends on population size N as well.

170 A strict NE can be pictured as corresponding to a particular vertex of
 171 the unit square (cf. Figure 2 with the axes scaled to be frequencies of the
 172 first strategy in each population instead of numbers and with vertices given
 173 as solid dots corresponding to strict NE). It is well-known (see Figs. 10.1,
 174 10.2, 11.1 in Hofbauer and Sigmund, 1998, or Figs. 3.3.1, 3.3.2, 3.3.3 in
 175 Cressman, 2003) that a classic two-strategy bimatrix game may have no
 176 strict NE, exactly one strict NE (e.g., Figure 2A), or exactly two strict NE
 177 that are diagonally opposite each other (e.g., Figure 2E). Furthermore, the
 178 classic two-strategy bimatrix game (with nondegenerate payoff bimatrix) can
 179 be classified by its strict NE and its interior NE (i.e., its unique NE where
 180 both populations are polymorphic) if it exists.

181 By examining interior NE, we will see this classification method fails
 182 for two-strategy time-constrained bimatrix games (see Section 2.2). These
 183 equilibria must satisfy $\Pi_{e_1} = \Pi_{e_2}$ and $\Pi_{f_1} = \Pi_{f_2}$ so that neither phenotype
 184 can increase its payoff by unilaterally switching its strategy. Unfortunately,
 185 obtaining analytic formulas for interior NE seems to be out of reach except
 186 in two special cases.

187 One special case is when interaction times satisfy $\tau_{12}\tau_{21} = \tau_{11}\tau_{22}$. Then
 188 the payoffs (9) evaluated at the equilibrium distribution (8) are the same as
 189 the payoffs for the classic bimatrix game with payoff matrix given by the
 190 time adjusted payoff matrix (10), i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_{e_i} &= \frac{N_{f_1} \pi_{i1}^e}{N \tau_{i1}} + \frac{N_{f_2} \pi_{i2}^e}{N \tau_{i2}} \\ \Pi_{f_j} &= \frac{N_{e_1} \pi_{1j}^f}{N \tau_{1j}} + \frac{N_{e_2} \pi_{2j}^f}{N \tau_{2j}}, \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

191 where $i, j = 1, 2$, and the interior NE simplifies to

$$(N_{e_1}, N_{f_1}) = \left(\frac{N\tau_{12}(\pi_{22}^f\tau_{21} - \pi_{21}^f\tau_{22})}{\tau_{22}(\pi_{11}^f\tau_{22} - \pi_{12}^f\tau_{21}) + \tau_{12}(\pi_{22}^f\tau_{21} - \pi_{21}^f\tau_{22})}, \right. \\ \left. \frac{N\tau_{21}(\pi_{22}^e\tau_{12} - \pi_{12}^e\tau_{22})}{\tau_{22}(\pi_{11}^e\tau_{22} - \pi_{12}^e\tau_{21}) + \tau_{12}(\pi_{22}^e\tau_{21} - \pi_{21}^e\tau_{22})} \right) \quad (12)$$

192 whenever both components are strictly between 0 and N . In fact, this is the
193 interior NE of the classic bimatrix game with time-adjusted bimatrix (10).

194 The other special case is interior symmetric NE (i.e., those on the main
195 diagonal where $N_{e_1} = N_{f_1}$) for role-independent time constrained bimatrix
196 games. As discussed in Section 2.2, there are up to two such diagonal interior
197 symmetric NE and the formulas for these are given in Křivan and Cressman
198 (2017).

199 To find interior NE in the general case, we can instead consider the repli-
200 cator equation at fixed population size N . This dynamics is given by³

$$\frac{dN_{e_1}}{dt} = \frac{N_{e_1}(N - N_{e_1})}{N}(\Pi_{e_1}(N_{e_1}, N_{f_1}) - \Pi_{e_2}(N_{e_1}, N_{f_1})) \\ \frac{dN_{f_1}}{dt} = \frac{N_{f_1}(N - N_{f_1})}{N}(\Pi_{f_1}(N_{e_1}, N_{f_1}) - \Pi_{f_2}(N_{e_1}, N_{f_1})) \quad (13)$$

201 where $\Pi_{e_i}(N_{e_1}, N_{f_1})$ and $\Pi_{f_i}(N_{e_1}, N_{f_1})$ are fitnesses (9) evaluated at the equi-
202 librium distribution (6) for a given (N_{e_1}, N_{f_1}) . Rest points of the replicator
203 equation with N_{e_1} and N_{f_1} strictly between 0 and N are the interior NE of the
204 underlying game (Hofbauer and Sigmund, 1998). Moreover, when all $\tau_{ij} = \tau$
205 are equal, the dynamics (13) is the replicator equation of the classic bimatrix
206 game (up to the factor τ that only affects the speed along trajectories and
207 not the evolutionary outcome).

208 Through the Owner-Intruder game with time-constraints, we illustrate
209 the two special cases mentioned above (i.e., either $\tau_{12}\tau_{21} = \tau_{11}\tau_{22}$ or interior
210 symmetric NE) as well as the replicator method for the general case.

³Replicator dynamics at fixed population size assume that frequencies of e_1 strategists p_1 are described by $\frac{dp_1}{dt} = p_1(1 - p_1)(\Pi_{e_1}(N_{e_1}, N_{f_1}) - \Pi_{e_2}(N_{e_1}, N_{f_1}))$ (Hofbauer and Sigmund, 1998). Because $N_{e_1} = p_1N$ and the overall size N of population 1 is assumed to be fixed, we obtain $\frac{dN_{e_1}}{dt} = \frac{dp_1}{dt}N$ which yields the first equation in (13).

211 *2.2. Owner–Intruder game*

212 The classic owner intruder game (Maynard Smith, 1982; Hofbauer and
 213 Sigmund, 1998; Cressman, 2003; Broom and Rychtář, 2013) is the two-role
 214 extension of the symmetric Hawk–Dove game (i.e., matrix game) that models
 215 the situation in which an individual either owns a site or is an intruder trying
 216 to seize a site. An individual can either be a Hawk (strategy e_1 if owner and
 217 f_1 if intruder) or a Dove (strategy e_2 if owner and f_2 if intruder) in either of
 218 the two roles. The payoff bimatrix of the game is

$$\begin{array}{c|cc} \text{Owner}\backslash\text{Intruder} & \text{Hawk} & \text{Dove} \\ \hline \text{Hawk} & \left[\frac{V-C}{2}, \frac{V-C}{2} \right] & [V, 0] \\ \text{Dove} & [0, V] & \left[\frac{V}{2}, \frac{V}{2} \right] \end{array}$$

219 where V (the value attached to the site) and C (the cost of fighting) are
 220 positive. It is an example of a role-independent bimatrix game since an
 221 individual’s payoff depends only on the strategies used in the interaction and
 222 not on whether the individual is the owner or the intruder.⁴

223 When the cost of fighting is low ($C < V$), the classic game has a single NE
 224 $(e_1, f_1) = (H, H)$ where individuals in both positions behave as hawks. When
 225 the cost of fighting is high ($C > V$) there are two strict NE $(e_2, f_1) = (D, H)$
 226 and $(e_1, f_2) = (H, D)$ as well as a mixed NE $(p_1, q_1) = (V/C, V/C)$, where
 227 Hawk strategy is played with probability V/C in both roles. This mixed NE
 228 cannot be a (two-species) ESS, because bimatrix games can have ESSs only
 229 in pure strategies (Selten, 1980).⁵

230 For the time-constrained bimatrix game, we first analyze its strict NE

⁴Broom and Rychtář (2013) refer to role independence as an “uncorrelated asymmetry” (see also the role games of Hofbauer and Sigmund (1998)). Mathematically, role independence is equivalent to the second payoff entries in the bimatrix forming the transpose of the matrix of first entries. It is assumed that the pure strategy sets for both roles are the same as well as the ordering of their elements. Typically, the strategies are given the same name in both roles (e.g., Hawk and Dove) and the same order. Every role-independent bimatrix game is the two-role extension of a symmetric matrix game and has NE where both populations use the same strategy; namely, a NE of the matrix game. In addition, there may be other NE.

⁵In fact, a strategy pair is an ESS for a classic bimatrix game if and only if it is a strict NE.

231 through the following time-adjusted bimatrix (cf. (10))

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \text{Owner}\backslash\text{Intruder} \\
 \text{Hawk} \\
 \text{Dove}
 \end{array}
 \begin{array}{cc}
 \text{Hawk} & \text{Dove} \\
 \left[\begin{array}{cc}
 \frac{V-C}{2\tau_{11}}, \frac{V-C}{2\tau_{11}} & \frac{V}{\tau_{12}}, 0 \\
 0, \frac{V}{\tau_{21}} & \frac{V}{2\tau_{22}}, \frac{V}{2\tau_{22}}
 \end{array} \right].
 \end{array}$$

232 The following list contains all strict NE of the time-constrained Owner–
 233 Intruder game (Figure 1). After each item in this list, the panels in Figure 2
 234 that have this strict NE are indicated in parentheses.

- 235 • If $V > C$, then strategy (H, H) is a NE (e.g., Figure 2A–D).
- 236 • If $\tau_{12} > 2\tau_{22}$ and $\tau_{21} > 2\tau_{22}$, then strategy (D, D) is a NE (e.g., Figure
 237 2B, F, G, H).
- 238 • If $V < C$ and $\tau_{12} < 2\tau_{22}$, then strategy (H, D) is a NE (e.g., Figure 2E,
 239 J).
- 240 • If $V < C$ and $\tau_{21} < 2\tau_{22}$, then strategy (D, H) is a NE (e.g., Figure
 241 2E, I).

242 Dependence of strict NEs as a function of model parameters are shown in
 243 Figure 1. There is at least one strict NE for all parameter values except in
 244 the degenerate situations where $V = C$, $\tau_{12} = 2\tau_{22}$, or $\tau_{21} = 2\tau_{22}$ (these are
 245 the dashed lines in Figure 1) that are discussed in Section 2.3.

246 Of particular note is that, although strategy pair (Dove, Dove) is never
 247 an ESS (i.e. a strict NE) for the classic Owner–Intruder game (since Dove
 248 is never an ESS for the Hawk–Dove matrix game), this pair is a strict NE
 249 when $2\tau_{22} < \min\{\tau_{12}, \tau_{21}\}$. This analysis shows that when compared with
 250 the classical model, the model that considers duration of interactions can
 251 have strategy (D, D) as a NE provided the interaction time between Doves
 252 is small.

In the special case where interaction times satisfy $\tau_{12}\tau_{21} = \tau_{11}\tau_{22}$, the interior NE (provided it exists) is given by (12) as

$$(N_{e_1}, N_{f_1}) = \left(\frac{N\tau_{12}V(\tau_{21} - 2\tau_{22})}{\tau_{22}^2(V - C) + \tau_{12}V(\tau_{21} - 2\tau_{22})}, \frac{N\tau_{21}V(\tau_{12} - 2\tau_{22})}{(V - C)\tau_{22}^2 + \tau_{21}V(\tau_{12} - 2\tau_{22})} \right).$$

253 We observe that when all interaction times are the same, the interior equilib-
 254 rium is $(N_{e_1}, N_{f_1}) = (V/C, V/C)$ exactly as in the classical Owner–Intruder
 255 game.

Figure 1: Strict NE of the Owner–Intruder game as functions of V and $2\tau_{22}$ parameters. Panel A assumes that $\tau_{21} < \tau_{12}$ and panel B assumes the opposite inequality.

256 To investigate interior NE further for the Owner–Intruder game, fitness
 257 functions (9) are now

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Pi_{e_1} &= \frac{n_{11}(V - C)}{2\tau_{11}(n_{11} + n_{12})} + \frac{n_{12}V}{\tau_{12}(n_{11} + n_{12})}, \\
 \Pi_{e_2} &= \frac{n_{22}V}{2\tau_{22}(n_{21} + n_{22})}, \\
 \Pi_{f_1} &= \frac{n_{11}(V - C)}{2\tau_{11}(n_{11} + n_{21})} + \frac{n_{21}V}{\tau_{21}(n_{11} + n_{21})}, \\
 \Pi_{f_2} &= \frac{n_{22}V}{2\tau_{22}(n_{12} + n_{22})}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

258 Evaluating these at the equilibrium distribution (6) yields

$$\begin{aligned}
\Pi_{e_1} &= \frac{(C\tau_{12} + (2\tau_{11} - \tau_{12})V)(\sqrt{A} - N\tau_{12}\tau_{21})}{4N_{e_1}\tau_{11}\tau_{12}(\tau_{11}\tau_{22} - \tau_{12}\tau_{21})} + \frac{\tau_{12}(V - C)(N_{e_1} + N_{f_1}) + 2\tau_{11}V(N_{e_1} - N_{f_1})}{4N_{e_1}\tau_{11}\tau_{12}} \\
\Pi_{e_2} &= - \frac{V \left(\sqrt{A} + N(\tau_{12}\tau_{21} - 2\tau_{11}\tau_{22}) - (N_{e_1} + N_{f_1})(\tau_{12}\tau_{21} - \tau_{11}\tau_{22}) \right)}{4\tau_{22}(N - N_{e_1})(\tau_{11}\tau_{22} - \tau_{12}\tau_{21})} \\
\Pi_{f_1} &= - \frac{\sqrt{A}(C\tau_{21} + (2\tau_{11} - \tau_{21})V)}{4N_{f_1}\tau_{11}\tau_{21}(\tau_{12}\tau_{21} - \tau_{11}\tau_{22})} + \frac{N\tau_{12}(C\tau_{21} + 2\tau_{11}V - \tau_{21}V)}{4N_{f_1}\tau_{11}(\tau_{12}\tau_{21} - \tau_{11}\tau_{22})} - \\
&\quad \frac{(C - V)(N_{e_1} + N_{f_1})}{4N_{f_1}\tau_{11}} + \frac{2\tau_{11}V(N_{f_1} - N_{e_1})}{4N_{f_1}\tau_{11}\tau_{21}} \\
\Pi_{f_2} &= - \frac{V \left(\sqrt{A} + N(\tau_{12}\tau_{21} - 2\tau_{11}\tau_{22}) - (N_{e_1} + N_{f_1})(\tau_{12}\tau_{21} - \tau_{11}\tau_{22}) \right)}{4\tau_{22}(N - N_{f_1})(\tau_{11}\tau_{22} - \tau_{12}\tau_{21})},
\end{aligned}$$

259 where A is given in (7). To find interior NE, we need to solve $\Pi_{e_1} = \Pi_{e_2}$ and
260 $\Pi_{f_1} = \Pi_{f_2}$.

261 Two-strategy, bimatrix games that are role-independent have role-independent
262 interaction times if and only if $\tau_{12} = \tau_{21}$ (i.e., the length of Hawk–Dove in-
263 teractions does not depend on whether the Hawk is the owner or the in-
264 truder).⁶ Symmetric NE of the role-independent time-constrained Owner–
265 Intruder game are then those of the time-constrained Hawk–Dove matrix
266 game, which are found analytically in Křivan and Cressman (2017) using
267 `Solve` command of Mathematica 11.

268 Since attempts to use this method to find interior NE when the time-
269 constrained bimatrix game was not role-independent or interaction times did
270 not satisfy $\tau_{12}\tau_{21} = \tau_{11}\tau_{22}$ failed, we now analyze the NE of the Owner–
271 Intruder game numerically through the replicator equation, focusing on the
272 cases where $V > C$ and $V < C$ separately.

273 First, assume that $V > C$ (Figure 2, panels A–D). Then (H, H) is al-
274 ways a strict NE. When the time-constrained Owner–Intruder game is role-
275 independent, the replicator equation is invariant along the main diagonal of
276 the unit square and its trajectories in the unit square are reflections in the
277 main diagonal (Figure 2A,B,C). Furthermore, on the diagonal, the dynamics

⁶We call a multi-strategy time-constrained bimatrix game “role-independent” if both its payoff bimatrix and its time interaction matrix are role-independent. This last requirement is equivalent to the time interaction matrix being symmetric (i.e., $\tau_{ij} = \tau_{ji}$ for all i, j).

278 (13) restricts to the replicator equation for the time-constrained Hawk–Dove
 279 matrix game, which was analyzed by Krivan and Cressman (2017). They
 280 showed that, when interaction times between two Hawks are long enough
 281 (and all other interaction times are the same), there exist two (symmetric)
 282 interior NEs and the one with fewer Hawks is locally asymptotically stable
 283 while the other one is unstable. However, numerical simulations (e.g., Figure
 284 2C) show that both interior symmetric NE (i.e., those gray points that are
 285 on the main diagonal) are saddles (i.e., unstable) for the bimatrix replicator
 286 dynamics.⁷

287 Simulations of the replicator equation for the role-independent time-constrained
 288 Owner–Intruder game with $V > C$ show that long interaction times between
 289 Hawks now lead to two new asymmetric interior NE (i.e., those off the main
 290 diagonal shown as black interior dots in Figure 2C). Numerical simulations
 291 suggest that these two equilibria are neutrally stable as they appear to be
 292 surrounded by a family of closed trajectories. The domain of the phase space
 293 filled by these closed curves is separated from the rest by two heteroclinic
 294 orbits that join the two symmetric NE. In particular, the symmetric strict
 295 NE (H, H) where all individuals play Hawk is not globally asymptotically
 296 stable.

297 The neutral stability of the asymmetric NE disappears when the time
 298 interaction matrix is role dependent. For example, it is reasonable to assume
 299 that interaction time between intruding Hawk and owning Dove is longer
 300 than that between intruding Dove and owning Hawk (i.e., $\tau_{21} > \tau_{12}$) because
 301 an owning Dove tries to defend its site against attacking Hawk. This role-
 302 dependent interaction time makes one of the two interior asymmetric NE
 303 unstable while the other becomes locally asymptotically stable (Figure 2D).

304 Now assume that $V < C$ (Figure 2, panels E–K). Hawk is no longer an
 305 ESS for the classic Hawk–Dove game and the only NE is the interior ESS
 306 where the population plays Hawk with probability $\frac{V}{C}$. On the other hand,

⁷From extensive simulations of the replicator equation, it seems likely that any interior symmetric NE of two-strategy role-independent time-constrained bimatrix games are always saddles but we have no proof of this conjecture. In the special case where $\tau_{12}\tau_{21} = \tau_{11}\tau_{22}$ (and $\tau_{12} = \tau_{21}$), interior symmetric NE are saddles since, from (11), Π_{e_1} (and Π_{f_1}) depends only on the strategy frequency of the other population, implying that the Jacobian of replicator dynamics (13) evaluated at interior equilibrium (12) has zeros on the main diagonal. This extends the same well-known result for classic role-independent bimatrix games (Hofbauer and Sigmund, 1998).

307 the classic Owner–Intruder game has two strict NE (H, D) and (D, H) ⁸ and
 308 the unstable interior NE where both populations plays Hawk with probabil-
 309 ity $\frac{V}{C}$. This corresponds to the time-constrained game with all interaction
 310 times equal (Figure 2E). When Hawk–Dove interactions are sufficiently long
 311 compared to Dove–Dove interactions (specifically, $\tau_{21} > 2\tau_{22}$ and $\tau_{12} > 2\tau_{22}$),
 312 then (D, D) is the only NE (Figure 2F). With a lower cost (Figure 2G),
 313 two symmetric interior NE appear (they are both saddles) along with two
 314 neutrally stable asymmetric interior NE that are surrounded by a family of
 315 closed trajectories. Furthermore, a small perturbation of these NE by in-
 316 troducing a slight role dependence in interaction times makes one of them
 317 locally asymptotically stable and the other unstable (panel H). Larger dif-
 318 ferences for role dependent interaction times (panels I and J respectively)
 319 eliminates interior NE altogether and make the paradoxical ESS (D, H) (re-
 320 spectively, (H, D)) globally asymptotically stable. Panel K is a degenerate
 321 case where $\tau_{12} = \tau_{21} = 2\tau_{22}$ and so has boundary NE as discussed in the
 322 following section. Finally, panel L assumes $V = C = 1$, $\tau_{11} = 3$ and all other
 323 interaction times are 1. This parametrization corresponds to the situation
 324 where sets of the NE along the boundary of square $[0, N] \times [0, N]$ exist. As
 325 calculated in the following section, the sets of NE are $0 \leq N_{e_1} < \frac{3}{4}N$ when
 326 $N_{f_1} = N$ and $0 \leq N_{f_1} < \frac{3}{4}N$ when $N_{e_1} = N$.

327 2.3. Boundary NE

328 The previous two sections analyzed the strict NE and interior NE for
 329 two-strategy time-constrained bimatrix games. These games may also have
 330 NE on an edge of the square that are not at a vertex (i.e., partially mixed
 331 NE where only one of the two populations is polymorphic). For example,
 332 suppose that population 1 is polymorphic and population 2 is monomorphic
 333 at pure strategy f_1 , i.e., $N_{f_1} = N$. Then, at a NE on this edge, the fitnesses
 334 of both strategies of population 1 must be equal, i.e., $\Pi_{e_1} = \Pi_{e_2}$. Since
 335 $n_{12} = n_{22} = 0$, $\Pi_{e_1} = \frac{\pi_{11}^e}{\tau_{11}}$ and $\Pi_{e_2} = \frac{\pi_{21}^e}{\tau_{21}}$ from (9).⁹ In this degenerate case
 336 where $\frac{\pi_{11}^e}{\tau_{11}} = \frac{\pi_{21}^e}{\tau_{21}}$, a point along the edge $N_{f_1} = N$ is a NE if and only if

⁸The second strict NE is often called the “paradoxical ESS” (Maynard Smith, 1982) since it corresponds to the intruder always taking over the site and becoming the owner.

⁹In classic two-strategy bimatrix games, the pure strategy pair (e_1, f_1) may be a NE in this situation but not a strict NE. We have ignored this degenerate case in the classification of pure strategy NE in Sections 2.1 and 2.2 of our time-constrained bimatrix game through (10) above.

337 $\Pi_{f_1} \geq \Pi_{f_2}$. Since $n_{21} = N_{e_2}$, $n_{11} = N_{e_1}$ and $N = N_{e_1} + N_{e_2}$,

$$\Pi_{f_1} = \frac{N_{e_1} \pi_{11}^f}{N \tau_{11}} + \frac{N_{e_2} \pi_{21}^f}{N \tau_{21}}. \quad (15)$$

338 On the other hand, the invasion fitness of strategy f_2 when there are no
339 individuals playing this strategy is (see Appendix B)

$$\Pi_{f_2} = \frac{N_{e_1} \pi_{12}^f \tau_{21} + N_{e_2} \pi_{22}^f \tau_{11}}{N \tau_{11} \tau_{22} + N_{e_1} (\tau_{12} \tau_{21} - \tau_{11} \tau_{22})}. \quad (16)$$

340 Solving $\Pi_{f_1} = \Pi_{f_2}$ gives us, in general, up to two roots for N_{e_1} satisfying
341 $0 \leq N_{e_1} \leq N$. These roots divide the edge into closed subintervals, on each
342 of which $\Pi_{f_1} - \Pi_{f_2}$ does not change sign. Each such subinterval with this
343 difference nonnegative is then a connected set of NE.¹⁰ However, since each
344 point on this edge is a rest point of the replicator equation, none can be
345 asymptotically stable under this dynamics.

346 For the Owner–Intruder game, boundary NE emerge on the top edge of
347 the square $[0, N] \times [0, N]$ where $N_{f_1} = N$ when $V = C$ since $\frac{\pi_{11}^e}{\tau_{11}} = \frac{\pi_{21}^e}{\tau_{21}} = 0$
348 along this edge. By evaluating when $\Pi_{f_1} \geq \Pi_{f_2}$ along this edge, we find the
349 following three cases for sets of NE of the form (N_{e_1}, N)

- 350 1. $\tau_{11} \leq 2\tau_{12}$ and $\tau_{21} < 2\tau_{22}$ and $0 \leq N_{e_1} \leq N$
- 351 2. $\tau_{11} > 2\tau_{12}$ and $\tau_{21} < 2\tau_{22}$ and $0 \leq N_{e_1} \leq \frac{N\tau_{11}(\tau_{21}-2\tau_{22})}{2(\tau_{12}\tau_{21}-\tau_{11}\tau_{22})}$
- 352 3. $\tau_{11} < 2\tau_{12}$ and $\tau_{21} \geq 2\tau_{22}$ and $\frac{N\tau_{11}(\tau_{21}-2\tau_{22})}{2(\tau_{12}\tau_{21}-\tau_{11}\tau_{22})} \leq N_{e_1} \leq N$

353 Similarly, let us consider the right edge of the square where all individuals
354 of the first species play strategy Hawk, i.e., $N_{e_1} = N$. When $V = C$, this
355 leads to the following sets of NE for the Owner–Intruder game.

- 356 1. $\tau_{11} \leq 2\tau_{21}$ and $\tau_{12} < 2\tau_{22}$ and $0 \leq N_{f_1} \leq N$
- 357 2. $\tau_{11} > 2\tau_{21}$ and $\tau_{12} < 2\tau_{22}$ and $0 \leq N_{f_1} \leq \frac{N\tau_{11}(\tau_{12}-2\tau_{22})}{2(\tau_{12}\tau_{21}-\tau_{11}\tau_{22})}$
- 358 3. $\tau_{11} < 2\tau_{21}$ and $\tau_{12} > 2\tau_{22}$ and $\frac{N\tau_{11}(\tau_{12}-2\tau_{22})}{2(\tau_{12}\tau_{21}-\tau_{11}\tau_{22})} \leq N_{f_1} \leq N$

359 These sets of NE on the boundary are illustrated in Figure 2L for the
360 role-independent time-constrained Owner–Intruder game with $V = C$. From
361 Křivan and Cressman (2017) the interior NE in this figure appears for $\tau_{11} >$

¹⁰In classical games, this set is called a NE component (Cressman, 2003).

362 $\tau(3 - C/V + 2\sqrt{1 - C/V}) = 2\tau$ (assuming $\tau_{12} = \tau_{22} = \tau$). In this case the
363 NEs on the edges form two disconnected components. Since $\tau_{12} = \tau_{21}$, the
364 NE component on the upper edge is then the reflection in the main diagonal
365 of the component on the right-hand edge.

366 We note that sets of NE also appear (Figure 2K) on the lower (re-
367 spectively, left-hand) edges of the square when $\tau_{12} = 2\tau_{22}$ (respectively,
368 $\tau_{21} = 2\tau_{22}$). By other choices of interaction time τ_{11} we can also get dis-
369 connected components along these edges.

Figure 2: The replicator dynamics for the Owner–Intruder game depending on V , C and interaction times when pairing is instantaneous. The first four panels (i.e., panels A, B, C, and D) assume $V > C$ (in fact, $V = 4$ and $C = 1$). The other panels assume $V = 1 \leq C$ with $C = 4$ (panels E, F, I, J, K), $C = 1.5$ (panels G, H) and $C = 1$ (panel L). All interaction times not equal to 1 are indicated in each panel. Thus, panels A and E respectively are the replicator dynamics of the classic Owner–Intruder game for $V > C$ and $V < C$ respectively since all interaction times are the same. In particular, the main diagonal is invariant in these two panels since the time-constrained game is role-independent. For the same reason, this invariance holds in panels B, C, F, G, K, L but not in the other four panels (D, H, I, J) that have role dependent interaction times (i.e., $\tau_{12} \neq \tau_{21}$). In panel B, strategy pairs (H, H) and (D, D) are strict NE (since $\min\{\tau_{12}, \tau_{21}\} > 2\tau_{22}$ and $V > C$) and an unstable saddle symmetric interior NE appears. In panel C, Hawk-Hawk interaction time is long enough ($\tau_{11} = 5$) that two unstable saddle symmetric interior NE emerge along with two neutrally stable asymmetric ones. Panel D is an asymmetric perturbation of the interaction time matrix from panel C (specifically τ_{12} shifts from 1 to 1.1) that perturbs the two asymmetric NE to a stable and unstable one. Since $\min\{\tau_{12}, \tau_{21}\} > 2\tau_{22}$ and $V < C$ in panels F, G, H, (D, D) is the only strict NE. It may be globally asymptotically stable (panel F) or only locally asymptotically stable when there are four interior NE with two unstable saddles and two neutrally stable (the role-independent case of panel G) or two unstable saddles together with one unstable and one stable NE (panel H with perturbed interaction matrix compared to panel G). In the role-dependent interaction matrices of panels I and J, τ_{12} (respectively τ_{21}) is large enough that the paradoxical ESS (D, H) (respectively (H, D)) is the only strict NE and it is globally asymptotically stable. Finally, panels K and L illustrate that sets of boundary NE emerge (thick black line segments) when $V = 1$, $C = 4$, $\tau_{11} = \tau_{12} = \tau_{21} = 2\tau_{22} = 1$ (panel K), and $V = C$ (panel L).

370 3. Non instantaneous pair formation

371 So far we have assumed that pair formation is instantaneous, i.e., there are
372 no singles. This assumption is natural in population genetics, where alleles
373 exist as singles only during meiosis but otherwise they are always paired in
374 diploid individuals. However, since it may be more realistic in general to
375 assume that it takes some time for singles to form pairs, we consider both
376 singles and paired individuals in this section. We also assume that, when
377 a pair disbands, these new singles are ready immediately to start searching
378 for new partners with encounter rate λ and new pairs are formed by random

379 encounters between one single from each population.¹¹

380 The number of singles of the two strategies for population 1 are denoted
 381 by n_{e_i} for $i = 1, 2$ and for population 2 by n_{f_j} for $j = 1, 2$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} N_{e_i} &= n_{e_i} + n_{i1} + n_{i2} \\ N_{f_j} &= n_{f_j} + n_{1j} + n_{2j} \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

382 are the total number of individuals playing a given strategy. We continue to
 383 assume that the total number of individuals in each population is N (i.e.,
 384 $N_{e_1} + N_{e_2} = N = N_{f_1} + N_{f_2}$).

385 Distributional dynamics of singles and pairs when pair formation is de-
 386 scribed by the mass action law are then

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dn_{e_1}}{dt} &= -\lambda n_{e_1}(n_{f_1} + n_{f_2}) + \frac{n_{11}}{\tau_{11}} + \frac{n_{12}}{\tau_{12}} \\ \frac{dn_{e_2}}{dt} &= -\lambda n_{e_2}(n_{f_1} + n_{f_2}) + \frac{n_{21}}{\tau_{21}} + \frac{n_{22}}{\tau_{22}} \\ \frac{dn_{f_1}}{dt} &= -\lambda n_{f_1}(n_{e_1} + n_{e_2}) + \frac{n_{11}}{\tau_{11}} + \frac{n_{21}}{\tau_{21}} \\ \frac{dn_{f_2}}{dt} &= -\lambda n_{f_2}(n_{e_1} + n_{e_2}) + \frac{n_{12}}{\tau_{12}} + \frac{n_{22}}{\tau_{22}} \\ \frac{dn_{11}}{dt} &= \lambda n_{e_1} n_{f_1} - \frac{n_{11}}{\tau_{11}} \\ \frac{dn_{12}}{dt} &= \lambda n_{e_1} n_{f_2} - \frac{n_{12}}{\tau_{12}} \\ \frac{dn_{21}}{dt} &= \lambda n_{e_2} n_{f_1} - \frac{n_{21}}{\tau_{21}} \\ \frac{dn_{22}}{dt} &= \lambda n_{e_2} n_{f_2} - \frac{n_{22}}{\tau_{22}}. \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

387 Appendix C shows that (18) has a unique distributional equilibrium for a
 388 fixed N and given N_{e_1} and N_{f_1} .

¹¹These last assumptions rule out applying the methods to bimatrix games where newly single individuals may wait after disbanding before they are ready to form new pairs. For example, in the model for parental care of offspring known as the Battle of the Sexes (Dawkins, 1976), when fast females mate with philandering males to produce offspring, it is assumed that the male immediately deserts and begins searching for a new mate whereas the female remains and cares for the offspring for a certain amount of time before searching for a new mate.

389 Assuming that singles do not get any payoffs, the fitnesses (i.e., the ex-
 390 pected payoff to an individual per unit time) of the four strategies evaluated
 391 at the unique equilibrium of (18) are ($i, j = 1, 2$)

$$\begin{aligned}\Pi_{e_i} &= \frac{n_{i1} \pi_{i1}^e}{N_{e_i} \tau_{i1}} + \frac{n_{i2} \pi_{i2}^e}{N_{e_i} \tau_{i2}}, \\ \Pi_{f_j} &= \frac{n_{1j} \pi_{1j}^f}{N_{f_j} \tau_{1j}} + \frac{n_{2j} \pi_{2j}^f}{N_{f_j} \tau_{2j}}.\end{aligned}\tag{19}$$

392 These fitness functions depend on N , N_{e_i} and N_{f_i} . Since, at the unique
 393 distributional equilibrium of (18),

$$n_{ij} = \lambda n_{e_i} n_{f_i} \tau_{ij}, \quad i, j = 1, 2\tag{20}$$

394 fitnesses (19) simplify to ($i, j = 1, 2$)

$$\begin{aligned}\Pi_{e_i} &= \frac{\lambda(n_{f_1} \pi_{i1}^e + n_{f_2} \pi_{i2}^e)}{\lambda n_{f_1} \tau_{i1} + \lambda n_{f_2} \tau_{i2} + 1}, \\ \Pi_{f_j} &= \frac{\lambda(n_{e_1} \pi_{1j}^f + n_{e_2} \pi_{2j}^f)}{\lambda n_{e_1} \tau_{1j} + \lambda n_{e_2} \tau_{2j} + 1}.\end{aligned}\tag{21}$$

395 The time-constrained bimatrix game with non instantaneous pair formation
 396 based on payoff bimatrix (1) and time interaction matrix (2) is then the two-
 397 strategy game with payoffs given by the fitness functions (21) evaluated at
 398 the distributional equilibrium of (18) for fixed size N of each population and
 399 encounter rate λ . As in Section 2, we are interested in the NE of this game
 400 and its evolutionary outcome.

401 3.1. Classic bimatrix game with non instantaneous pair formation

402 The classic model implicitly assumes all interaction times are equal (i.e.,
 403 $\tau_{ij} = \tau$ for all $i, j = 1, 2$). However, since the classic model also assumes that
 404 individuals are always interacting (i.e., always in pairs), the question arises
 405 whether the classic predictions remain valid when pair formation requires
 406 time. This section examines the question.

407 The equilibrium distribution of (18) is

$$\begin{aligned}n_{e_i} &= \frac{N_{e_i} (\sqrt{4\lambda N \tau} + 1 - 1)}{N \cdot 2\lambda N \tau} \\ n_{f_j} &= \frac{N_{f_j} (\sqrt{4\lambda N \tau} + 1 - 1)}{N \cdot 2\lambda N \tau}.\end{aligned}$$

408 Substituting these expressions to (21) leads to

$$\begin{aligned}\Pi_{e_i} &= \frac{4N\lambda}{(1 + \sqrt{1 + 4\lambda\tau N})^2} \left(\pi_{i1}^e \frac{N_{f_1}}{N} + \pi_{i2}^e \frac{N_{f_2}}{N} \right), \\ \Pi_{f_j} &= \frac{4N\lambda}{(1 + \sqrt{1 + 4\lambda\tau N})^2} \left(\pi_{1j}^f \frac{N_{e_1}}{N} + \pi_{2j}^f \frac{N_{e_2}}{N} \right).\end{aligned}\tag{22}$$

409 Thus, up to the positive factor $\frac{4N\lambda}{(1 + \sqrt{1 + 4\lambda\tau N})^2}$, these are the payoffs of the
 410 classic bimatrix game with payoff matrix (1). From this it follows that the
 411 NE of the classic bimatrix game with non instantaneous pair formation is
 412 the same as the the classic bimatrix game and, moreover, the trajectories of
 413 the replicator equation are the same (up to the speed along the trajectory).
 414 Thus, the two games have the same evolutionary outcomes.

415 To rephrase, standard evolutionary game theory models of bimatrix games
 416 can explicitly incorporate time constraints without affecting the game-theoretic
 417 analysis as long as all interaction times are the same. It is then irrelevant
 418 whether pair formation is instantaneous or requires some time.

419 3.2. Evolutionary outcomes with non instantaneous pair formation

420 As we saw in Section 2, evolutionary outcomes of time-constrained bima-
 421 trix games with instantaneous pair formation depend heavily on pair inter-
 422 action times when these are not all the same (e.g., Figure 2). This section
 423 analyzes the same phenomena when pair formation is not instantaneous.

424 We start by characterizing the strict NE of these games. From (21), at
 425 strategy pair (e_1, f_1) ,

$$\Pi_{e_1} = \frac{\lambda n_{f_1} \pi_{11}^e}{\lambda n_{f_1} \tau_{11} + 1}, \quad \Pi_{f_1} = \frac{\lambda n_{e_1} \pi_{11}^f}{\lambda n_{e_1} \tau_{11} + 1},$$

426 since $n_{e_2} = n_{f_2} = 0$. Note that the fitness Π_{e_1} (Π_{f_1}) does not depend on
 427 distributional equilibrium of population 1 (2). Thus, the invasion fitnesses
 428 of strategy e_2 and f_2 are

$$\Pi_{e_2} = \frac{\lambda n_{f_1} \pi_{21}^e}{\lambda n_{f_1} \tau_{21} + 1}$$

429 and

$$\Pi_{f_2} = \frac{\lambda n_{e_1} \pi_{12}^f}{\lambda n_{e_1} \tau_{12} + 1}$$

430 as given in (21) with $n_{e_2} = n_{f_2} = 0$. Furthermore, at this strategy pair,
 431 $N = n_{e_1} + n_{11} = n_{e_1} + \lambda n_{e_1} n_{f_1} \tau_{11} = n_{f_1} + n_{11}$. Thus, $n_{e_1} = n_{f_1}$ and so
 432 $N = \lambda \tau_{11} n_{e_1}^2 + n_{e_1}$ and

$$n_{e_1} = \frac{-1 + \sqrt{1 + 4N\lambda\tau_{11}}}{2\lambda\tau_{11}} = n_{f_1}.$$

433 Strategy pair (e_1, f_1) is a strict NE provided $\Pi_{e_1} > \Pi_{e_2}$ and $\Pi_{f_1} > \Pi_{f_2}$, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\pi_{11}^e}{\tau_{11}(\sqrt{4\lambda N\tau_{11} + 1} + 1)} &> \frac{\pi_{21}^e}{\tau_{21}(\sqrt{4\lambda N\tau_{11} + 1} - 1) + 2\tau_{11}} \\ \frac{\pi_{11}^f}{\tau_{11}(\sqrt{4\lambda N\tau_{11} + 1} + 1)} &> \frac{\pi_{12}^f}{\tau_{12}(\sqrt{4\lambda N\tau_{11} + 1} - 1) + 2\tau_{11}}. \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

434 Similarly, we can obtain conditions for other strict NE. Contrary to the case
 435 of instantaneous pairing where these conditions are given by the adjusted
 436 payoff matrix (10), we cannot write these conditions in a similar form when
 437 pairing is non-instantaneous. This is seen from expressions (23), where the
 438 invasion fitness for strategy e_2 (f_2) depends not only on interaction time τ_{21}
 439 (τ_{12}), but also on interaction time τ_{11} .

440 As λ increases to infinity, payoff Π_{e_1} (Π_{f_1}) converges to π_{11}^e/τ_{11} (π_{11}^f/τ_{11})
 441 and invasion fitness Π_{e_2} (Π_{f_2}) converges to π_{21}^e/τ_{21} (π_{12}^f/τ_{12}). Thus, when
 442 the encounter rate of singles is large, the strict NE of the time-constrained
 443 bimatrix game with non instantaneous pair formation are the same as the
 444 strict NE of the time-constrained bimatrix game of Section 2 (i.e., with in-
 445 stantaneous pair formation). In fact, for large λ , the interior NE match as
 446 well since there are essentially no singles in the system.

447 The next section illustrates these general results for the Owner–Intruder
 448 game.

449 3.3. The Owner–Intruder game with non instantaneous pair formation

450 When all interaction times equal to τ as in Section 3.1, there is an interior
 451 NE if and only if $V < C$. As a function of λ and τ , it is given by

$$\begin{aligned} n_{e_1} = n_{f_1} &= \frac{V(-1 + \sqrt{1 + 4\lambda N\tau})}{2C\lambda\tau} \\ n_{e_2} = n_{f_2} &= \frac{(C - V)(-1 + \sqrt{4\lambda N\tau})}{2C\lambda\tau} \\ N_{e_1} = N_{f_1} &= \frac{NV}{C}, \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

452 which is the classic result for the case when $V < C$.

453 However, for a general time interaction matrix, an analytic expression
454 for the interior NE is not available. Our recourse is to apply the replica-
455 tor equation (13) with payoffs (21) when pairing is non-instantaneous. On
456 contrary to the case of instantaneous pairing, we cannot now express the dis-
457 tributional equilibrium at the current strategy numbers explicitly. Thus, we
458 have to solve replicator equation (13) together with the system of algebraic
459 equations

$$\begin{aligned} N_{e_1} &= n_{e_1}(1 + \lambda n_{f_1} \tau_{11} + \lambda n_{f_2} \tau_{12}) \\ N_{f_1} &= n_{f_1}(1 + \lambda n_{e_1} \tau_{11} + \lambda n_{e_2} \tau_{21}). \end{aligned} \tag{25}$$

460 This is a semi-explicit index 1 differential-algebraic equation (Ascher and
461 Petzold, 1998) that we solve numerically using Mathematica 10.

462 Figure 3 shows the results for two encounter rates. Panels A–H use the
463 same parameter values (i.e., V , C , τ_{ij}) as corresponding panels in Figure 2.
464 For the role-independent time-constrained cases (panels A–C, E–G), trajec-
465 tories remain reflections of each other with respect to the main diagonal. We
466 see that for large enough encounter rate ($\lambda = 10$ in panels A–H) the strict
467 NE still match those of Section 2. However, there are differences in stability
468 of interior NE between Figures 2 and 3. The neutral stability of the two
469 off-diagonal equilibria in Figure 2C and G is lost and the two equilibria be-
470 come unstable. Figure 3C and G show two trajectories that start close to the
471 two equilibria and that converge to equilibrium $(N_{e_1}, N_{f_1}) = (100, 100)$ and
472 $(N_{e_1}, N_{f_1}) = (0, 0)$, respectively. Panels C', D', G', and H' show numerical
473 simulations for yet smaller encounter rate ($\lambda = 1$). We observe that this leads
474 to disappearance of interior NE in panels C' and D', and to destabilization of
475 the interior stable NE in panel H that is replaced by a locally stable limit cy-
476 cle in panel H'. These numerical simulations, for the parameter values used,
477 show that small and intermediate encounter rates make coexistence of both
478 strategies in polymorphic state less likely.

Figure 3: The replicator dynamics for the Owner–Intruder game when pairing is not instantaneous. For role-independent time-constrained bimatrix games (panels A, B, C, E, F, G, C', G'), the main diagonal remains invariant. The encounter rate between singles is $\lambda = 10$ in panels A–H and $\lambda = 1$ in panels C'–H'. Other parameters are the same as in the corresponding panels of Figure 2. Panels A and E are identical to their corresponding panels in Figure 2 since these are all equivalent to the classic bimatrix game. There are also no noticeable differences between panels B and F compared to Figure 2. The differences with Figure 2 (which emerges for very large λ) are as follows. For long interaction times between Hawks when $V > C$, the four interior NE of Figure 2 disappear completely when $\lambda = 1$ (panels C' and D') whereas the two asymmetric interior NE become unstable for intermediate λ (panel C). When the interaction time between Doves is short and $V < C$, the asymmetric interior NE of the role-independent time-constrained bimatrix game lose stability and the two symmetric interior shift apart as λ decreases (panels G and G'). With role-dependent interaction times, the asymptotically stable interior NE of Figure 2H eventually becomes unstable when λ decreases and a stable limit cycle emerges.

479 **4. Discussion**

480 This article extends to two-strategy bimatrix games the new approach
 481 to evolutionary game theory developed by Krivan and Cressman (2017) for
 482 two-player, two-strategy, symmetric normal form games (i.e., matrix games)
 483 that incorporates the effect pair interaction times that depend on the play-
 484 ers' strategies have on the evolutionary outcome. Evolutionary game theory
 485 applied to bimatrix games is based on two populations (or two roles) where
 486 individuals interact in pairs, one from each population. Classical bimatrix
 487 games, similarly to matrix games, assume that individuals get payoffs when
 488 paired, pairing is random and instantaneous, and the number of different
 489 types of pairs is given by the Hardy–Weinberg distribution. The evolution-
 490 ary outcome of the bimatrix game is then predicted through an analysis of
 491 the NE structure of its payoff bimatrix and how this is connected to the
 492 eventual behavior of the game dynamics (e.g., the replicator equation). A
 493 complete analysis of the evolutionary outcome is well-known for all classi-
 494 cal two-strategy bimatrix games (Hofbauer and Sigmund, 1998; Cressman,
 495 2003).

496 When interaction times depend on strategies used by the pair, the Hardy–
 497 Weinberg distribution of pairs is no longer relevant and expected individual

498 payoff is now a nonlinear function of the numbers using each strategy in the
499 two populations whether the pair formation process among disbanded pairs
500 is instantaneous (Section 2) or not (Section 3). However, in both cases, we
501 show the existence of a unique distribution as a function of these numbers
502 at the beginning of these respective sections,¹² although we are only able to
503 provide an analytic expression for it when pair formation is instantaneous
504 (see equation (6)). Nevertheless, this allows us to define a time-constrained,
505 bimatrix game in Section 2 and in Section 3 where payoff (which we call the
506 fitness function) is given as expected individual payoff per unit time. As
507 pointed out in Sections 2 and 3.1, this new formulation reduces to the classic
508 bimatrix game when all interaction times are the same.

509 What is then of interest is how different interaction times affect the evo-
510 lutionary outcome. To this end, we completely characterized strict NE for all
511 two-strategy, time-constrained, bimatrix games (Sections 2.1 and 3.2 respec-
512 tively). When pairing is instantaneous (Sections 2.1) strict NE are charac-
513 terized through their time-adjusted payoff matrices (10). A strict NE corre-
514 sponds to a locally asymptotically stable rest point of the replicator equation
515 where both populations use one of their pure strategies as indicated by solid
516 dots at vertices of the squares of Figures 2 and 3 respectively.

517 Unfortunately, other NE of the time-constrained bimatrix game are more
518 difficult to analyze. In particular, the analytic formula for interior NE is not
519 available except in special circumstances due to the complicated distribution
520 that replaces the Hardy–Weinberg distribution in these games. Since inter-
521 ior NE correspond to interior rest points of the replicator equation, they
522 can be approximated by simulating this dynamics for particular games. No
523 attempt is made for a complete analysis of all two-strategy time-constrained
524 bimatrix games.¹³ Instead, we focus on the time-constrained Owner–Intruder
525 game. This classic role-independent bimatrix game has an easily understood
526 evolutionary outcome.

527 When the cost of fighting over a resource C is less than its value V ,
528 both the owner of the resource and the intruder should fight for it (i.e., both

¹²In Section 3, this includes the distribution of pairs and singles

¹³The difficulty of doing such an analysis can be appreciated by considering the complete analysis for the two-locus two-allele viability selection model of population genetics. Pontz et al. (2018) show that this two-dimensional dynamics on the unit square has at least 192 different phase portraits. We feel our model will have a comparable (or even higher) number of different cases.

529 play Hawk) even though their payoff by doing so is less than if they split
530 the resource without fighting (i.e., both play Dove) in the classic bimatrix
531 game.¹⁴ The reason is that Hawk strictly dominates Dove in each population.
532 Although (Hawk, Hawk) remains a strict NE in the time-constrained bimatrix
533 game, other NE emerge as interaction times change. From panel B of Figures
534 2 and 3, we see that (Dove, Dove) can also be a strict NE (in which case there
535 is also an interior NE) when their interaction time is short enough compared
536 to the equal time of the other interactions. Furthermore, while (Dove, Dove)
537 is not a strict NE if only (Hawk, Hawk) interaction time changes, up to four
538 interior NE can appear if this interaction time is large enough, some of which
539 are (neutrally) stable and some unstable (panels C and D).

540 When $V < C$, (Hawk, Hawk) is never a strict NE. In the classic bimatrix
541 game, there are two strict NE; namely, (Hawk, Dove) and the paradoxical
542 ESS (Dove, Hawk) where the intruder always wins the resource (i.e., the
543 owner and intruder switch roles through each interaction) as well as one
544 unstable saddle symmetric interior NE where both populations play the ESS
545 of the classic symmetric Hawk–Dove matrix game. The replicator equation
546 predicts the paradoxical ESS will be the evolutionary outcome if and only
547 if the initial population distribution has more Hawks as intruders than as
548 owners. As shown in Figure 2, panels I and J, either one of these strict NE
549 can disappear by introducing a role dependence into the time interaction
550 matrix (2). In fact, both must disappear when (Dove, Dove) becomes a
551 strict NE through their interaction time being short enough compared to the
552 equal time of the other interactions in Figures 2 and 3, in which case interior
553 NE may (panels G and H) or may not appear (panel F). There are also
554 marked differences between the evolutionary outcomes when pair formation
555 is instantaneous compared to when it is non instantaneous, as detailed in the
556 main text.

557 In this article, although we have relaxed the implicit assumption of classic
558 evolutionary game theory that all interactions take the same amount of time,
559 we have assumed that newly single individuals are immediately available
560 to form pairs. This rules out straightforward application of our methods
561 to models where some single individuals from a disbanded pair wait before

¹⁴The same result occurs for the bimatrix version of the Prisoner’s Dilemma game where both players Defect at the evolutionary outcome even though they would be better off if both Cooperate.

562 joining the pair formation process. For instance, this occurs in parental care
563 models, e.g., Battle of the Sexes (Dawkins, 1976; Hofbauer and Sigmund,
564 1998; Mylius, 1999; Cressman, 2003; Broom and Rychtář, 2013) when males
565 are immediately available to mate after a couple disbands whereas females
566 will not mate immediately but stay to care for offspring if abandoned by their
567 mate. In this article, we assume that both populations have the same number
568 of individuals, which is required when pair formation is instantaneous. On
569 the other hand, when pair formation is non-instantaneous, all calculations
570 can be generalized to population 1 having a different size than population 2,
571 although the formulas are more complex.¹⁵

572 In this article, we have generalized two-strategy bimatrix games by explic-
573 itly including interaction times when pure strategists from each population
574 are paired. When applied to the classic Owner-Intruder game where each
575 individual, at given interaction, is either a Hawk or a Dove, we have a model
576 where owners and intruders have a choice between two levels of effort when
577 engaged in a conflict (Hawks are willing to expend a great deal of time and
578 effort to obtain the resource while Doves are not). Another approach to
579 this conflict situation is to allow intermediate levels of effort, resulting in a
580 time-constrained Owner-Intruder game with a continuum of pure strategies.
581 In the classic game with continuous strategy sets (for a recent review see
582 Cressman and Apaloo, 2018), the analysis of NE that have additional prop-
583 erties such as Continuously Stable Strategy (CSS) or Neighborhood Invader
584 Strategy (NIS) are particularly important. Although beyond the scope of
585 this article, it is then essential to first understand the effect of interaction
586 times on these concepts of CSS and NIS.

587 The results of this article show that the evolutionary outcome for bimatrix
588 games becomes more complex when interaction times are incorporated into
589 the game-theoretic model. The results are also more complex than those
590 reported by Křivan and Cressman (2017) for matrix games with strategy-
591 dependent interaction times as is to be expected given the conceptual dif-
592 ferences between classic matrix and bimatrix games. It is our contention
593 that these added complexities are often unavoidable to make the evolution-
594 ary model more realistic. This is especially true when the model purports
595 to describe a behavioral system where pairs interact for different amounts of

¹⁵With unequal population size, the time-constrained bimatrix game with all τ_{ij} equal is no longer the classic bimatrix game as in Section 3.1.

596 time.

597 **Acknowledgement**

598 This project has received funding from the European Union Horizon 2020
599 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant
600 agreement No 690817. VK acknowledges support provided by the Institute
601 of Entomology (RVO:60077344) and RC by an NSERC of Canada Individual
602 Discovery grant 7822. We also thank the two referees and the Handling
603 Editor for their encouraging comments on the original submission.

604 **Appendix A. Pairs distributional dynamics when pairing is in-**
 605 **stantaneous**

606 Here we derive pair dynamics (3). Let us consider a small time interval
 607 Δ . Because pairs n_{ij} split up following a Poisson process with parameter τ_{ij} ,
 608 in this time interval a proportion $\frac{\Delta}{\tau_{ij}}$ of the n_{ij} pairs disbands and there will
 609 be $(\frac{n_{i1}}{\tau_{i1}} + \frac{n_{i2}}{\tau_{i2}})\Delta$ singles playing strategy e_i and $(\frac{n_{1j}}{\tau_{1j}} + \frac{n_{2j}}{\tau_{2j}})\Delta$ singles playing
 610 strategy f_j . The total number of disbanded singles in each population in
 611 time interval Δ is

$$\left(\frac{n_{11}}{\tau_{11}} + \frac{n_{12}}{\tau_{12}} + \frac{n_{21}}{\tau_{21}} + \frac{n_{22}}{\tau_{22}} \right) \Delta. \quad (\text{A.1})$$

612 If these singles immediately and randomly pair, the proportion of newly
 613 formed n_{ij} pairs among all newly formed pairs will be

$$\frac{\left(\frac{n_{i1}}{\tau_{i1}} + \frac{n_{i2}}{\tau_{i2}} \right) \Delta}{\left(\frac{n_{11}}{\tau_{11}} + \frac{n_{12}}{\tau_{12}} + \frac{n_{21}}{\tau_{21}} + \frac{n_{22}}{\tau_{22}} \right) \Delta} \frac{\left(\frac{n_{1j}}{\tau_{1j}} + \frac{n_{2j}}{\tau_{2j}} \right) \Delta}{\left(\frac{n_{11}}{\tau_{11}} + \frac{n_{12}}{\tau_{12}} + \frac{n_{21}}{\tau_{21}} + \frac{n_{22}}{\tau_{22}} \right) \Delta}. \quad (\text{A.2})$$

614 To obtain the number of newly formed $(e_i f_j)$ pairs in the time interval Δ
 615 we multiply (A.2) by the number of newly formed pairs (which equals the
 616 number of disbanded singles because we assume instantaneous pairing) in
 617 time interval Δ and we obtain

$$\frac{\left(\frac{n_{i1}}{\tau_{i1}} + \frac{n_{i2}}{\tau_{i2}} \right) \left(\frac{n_{1j}}{\tau_{1j}} + \frac{n_{2j}}{\tau_{2j}} \right)}{\frac{n_{11}}{\tau_{11}} + \frac{n_{12}}{\tau_{12}} + \frac{n_{21}}{\tau_{21}} + \frac{n_{22}}{\tau_{22}}} \Delta.$$

618 Writing difference equations for pairs

$$n_{ij}(t + \Delta) = n_{ij}(t) - \frac{n_{ij}(t)}{\tau_{ij}} \Delta + \frac{\left(\frac{n_{i1}(t)}{\tau_{i1}} + \frac{n_{i2}(t)}{\tau_{i2}} \right) \left(\frac{n_{1j}(t)}{\tau_{1j}} + \frac{n_{2j}(t)}{\tau_{2j}} \right)}{\frac{n_{11}(t)}{\tau_{11}} + \frac{n_{12}(t)}{\tau_{12}} + \frac{n_{21}(t)}{\tau_{21}} + \frac{n_{22}(t)}{\tau_{22}}} \Delta \quad (\text{A.3})$$

619 and letting $\Delta \rightarrow 0_+$, we obtain the pair dynamics (3) in the main text.

620 From

$$\begin{aligned} N_{e_1} &= n_{11} + n_{12} \\ N_{f_1} &= n_{11} + n_{21} \\ N_{e_2} &= N - N_{e_1} \\ N_{f_2} &= N - N_{f_1} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

621 and the generalized Hardy–Weinberg equation (5), Mathematica provides
 622 two equilibrium solutions for n_{ij} in terms of N , N_{e_1} and N_{f_1} . However, only
 623 the one given in (6) is non-negative when $0 \leq N_{e_1}, N_{f_1} \leq N$.

624 It is not immediately clear that $A \geq 0$ where A is given in (7). To see
 625 this, expand A as the following quadratic expression in N_{e_1}

$$A = N_{e_1}^2 (\tau_{12}\tau_{21} - \tau_{11}\tau_{22})^2 - 2N_{e_1} (\tau_{12}\tau_{21} - \tau_{11}\tau_{22}) (N\tau_{12}\tau_{21} - N_{f_1}(\tau_{11}\tau_{22} + \tau_{12}\tau_{21})) +$$

$$(\tau_{12}\tau_{21}(N - N_{f_1}) + N_{f_1}\tau_{11}\tau_{22})^2 = aN_{e_1}^2 + bN_{e_1} + c.$$

626 The minimum value of this upward parabola is

$$c - \frac{b^2}{2a} = 4N_{f_1}\tau_{11}\tau_{12}\tau_{21}\tau_{22}(N - N_{f_1}).$$

627 Since $0 \leq N_{f_1} \leq N$, this minimum is non-negative and so $A \geq 0$.

628 Appendix B. Calculation of the invasion fitness (16)

629 The fitness of strategy f_2 , Π_{f_2} , given in (9) calculated at the distributional
 630 equilibrium (6) is

$$\Pi_{f_2} = \frac{\sqrt{A}(\pi_{22}^f \tau_{12} - \pi_{12}^f \tau_{22}) + N\tau_{12}(\pi_{12}^f \tau_{21} \tau_{22} - 2\pi_{22}^f \tau_{11} \tau_{22} + \pi_{22}^f \tau_{12} \tau_{21})}{2\tau_{12}\tau_{22}(N - N_{f_1})(\tau_{12}\tau_{21} - \tau_{11}\tau_{22})} -$$

$$\frac{(\tau_{12}\tau_{21} - \tau_{11}\tau_{22})(\pi_{12}^f \tau_{22}(N_{f_1} - N_{e_1}) + \pi_{22}^f \tau_{12}(N_{e_1} + N_{f_1}))}{2\tau_{12}\tau_{22}(N - N_{f_1})(\tau_{12}\tau_{21} - \tau_{11}\tau_{22})},$$

631 where A is given in (7). The invasion fitness of strategy f_2 when there are
 632 no individuals playing this strategy is then $\lim_{N_{f_1} \rightarrow N} \Pi_{f_2}$. We observe that

$$\lim_{N_{f_1} \rightarrow N} A = (N\tau_{11}\tau_{22} + N_{e_1}(\tau_{12}\tau_{21} - \tau_{11}\tau_{22}))^2.$$

633 Since $N \geq N_{e_1}$, $N\tau_{11}\tau_{22} + N_{e_1}(\tau_{12}\tau_{21} - \tau_{11}\tau_{22}) \geq 0$,

$$\lim_{N_{f_1} \rightarrow N} \sqrt{A} = N\tau_{11}\tau_{22} + N_{e_1}(\tau_{12}\tau_{21} - \tau_{11}\tau_{22})$$

634 and the numerator of Π_{f_2} simplifies to

$$(N - N_{f_1})(\pi_{12}^f \tau_{22} + \pi_{22}^f \tau_{12})(\tau_{12}\tau_{21} - \tau_{11}\tau_{22}).$$

635 Thus, both the numerator and denominator of Π_{f_2} converge to 0 when $N_{f_1} \rightarrow$
636 N and we calculate the limit using L'Hospital's rule

$$\lim_{N_{f_1} \rightarrow N} \Pi_{f_2} = \frac{N_{e_1} \pi_{12}^f \tau_{21} + N_{e_2} \pi_{22}^f \tau_{11}}{N \tau_{11} \tau_{22} + N_{e_1} (\tau_{12} \tau_{21} - \tau_{11} \tau_{22})}. \quad (\text{B.1})$$

637 Similarly, the fitness of strategy e_2 , Π_{e_2} , given in (9) calculated at the
638 distributional equilibrium (6) is

$$\Pi_{e_2} = \frac{\sqrt{A}(\pi_{22}^e \tau_{21} - \pi_{21}^e \tau_{22}) + N \tau_{21} (\pi_{21}^e \tau_{12} \tau_{22} - 2\pi_{22}^2 \tau_{11} \tau_{22} + \pi_{22}^2 \tau_{12} \tau_{21})}{2\tau_{21} \tau_{22} (N - N_{21}) (\tau_{12} \tau_{21} - \tau_{11} \tau_{22})} - \frac{(\tau_{12} \tau_{21} - \tau_{11} \tau_{22}) (\pi_{21}^e \tau_{22} (N_{e_1} - N_{f_1}) + \pi_{22}^e \tau_{21} (N_{e_1} + N_{f_1}))}{2\tau_{21} \tau_{22} (N - N_{e_1}) (\tau_{12} \tau_{21} - \tau_{11} \tau_{22})}.$$

639 The invasion fitness of strategy e_2 when there are no individuals playing this
640 strategy is

$$\lim_{N_{e_1} \rightarrow N} \Pi_{e_2} = \frac{N_{f_1} \pi_{21}^e \tau_{12} + N_{f_2} \pi_{22}^e \tau_{11}}{N \tau_{11} \tau_{22} + N_{f_1} (\tau_{12} \tau_{21} - \tau_{11} \tau_{22})} \quad (\text{B.2})$$

641 by again applying L'Hospital's rule.

642 Appendix C. Uniqueness of distributional equilibrium of (25)

643 Fix N_{e_i} and N_{f_i} ($i = 1, 2$) and define $q_{e_i} = \frac{n_{e_i}}{N_{e_i}}$ ($q_{f_i} = \frac{n_{f_i}}{N_{f_i}}$) as the pro-
644 portion of e_i (f_j) strategists in the population who are single. From (25) it
645 follows that

$$\begin{aligned} q_{e_1} &= \frac{1}{1 + \lambda N_{f_1} q_{f_1} \tau_{11} + \lambda N_{f_2} q_{f_2} \tau_{12}} \\ q_{e_2} &= \frac{1}{1 + \lambda N_{f_1} q_{f_1} \tau_{21} + \lambda N_{f_2} q_{f_2} \tau_{22}} \\ q_{f_1} &= \frac{1}{1 + \lambda N_{e_1} q_{e_1} \tau_{11} + \lambda N_{e_2} q_{e_2} \tau_{21}} \\ q_{f_2} &= \frac{1}{1 + \lambda N_{e_1} q_{e_1} \tau_{12} + \lambda N_{e_2} q_{e_2} \tau_{22}}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.1})$$

646 By Lemma 2 in Garay et al. (2017), there is a unique solution with q_{e_i} and
647 q_{f_j} between 0 and 1.

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649 **References**

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